

Short communication

Tenothrips ononidis (Thysanoptera: Thripidae): first record from Iran

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اولین گزارش *Tenothrips ononidis* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) از ایران

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چکیده

شمشین گونه از جنس *Tenothrips* با نام *Tenothrips ononidis* (Bournier) برای نخستین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود. وجود یک جفت اندام حسی کامپانی فرم روی پس‌گرده و نابرابری جفت موهای گوشه کناری پیش‌گرده، این گونه را از دیگر گونه‌های گزارش شده از ایران جدا می‌کند. نگاره‌های قسمت‌های مهم گونه یاد شده ارائه شده است.

واژه‌های کلیدی: *Tenothrips*، استان فارس، گزارش جدید.

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Up to now, five species of *Tenothrips* namely, *T. discolor* (Karny), *T. frici* (Uzel), *T. hispanicus* (Bagnall), *T. latoides* (Pelikan) and *T. reichardti* (Priesner) have been recorded from Iran (Afsharizadeh Bami & Minaei, 2020). In this report, another species of the genus is recorded for the first time from this country. Thrips specimens were mounted onto slides in Hoyer's medium using the protocol given by Mound & Kibby (1998). Photomicrographs were made using an Olympus BX51 phase-contrast microscope with DP27 digital camera and cellSens software. The specimen is deposited in the Department of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture, Shiraz University, Shiraz, Iran.

Tenothrips ononidis (Bournier)

Taeniothrips ononidis Bournier, 1962: 41.

Tenothrips ononidis was originally described from Frankreich, France based on female specimens collected on a legume plant, *Ononis minutissima* (Fabaceae) (Bournier, 1962). Subsequently one female specimen is reported from Morocco on *Teucrium chardonianum* (Lamiaceae) (zur Strassen, 1968). The species also reported from Spain (zur Strassen, 2000; 2003). Here, it is firstly recorded from Iran based on one female collected on an amaranth

plant. Considering that the male is not discovered yet, it seems likely that the species is rare. Available information does not support any specific host plant for *Tenothrips onondis*.

Diagnosis: Female fully winged (Fig. 1). Body light brown, legs mostly yellow; antennal segment I yellow, II brown, III–VI almost yellowish brown but shading to brown apically, VII–VIII brown (Fig. 7); fore wings pale (Fig. 8); pronotum yellow-brown (Fig. 2), major setae brown. Head slightly wider than long; antennae 8-segmented; segments III & IV each with a forked sense cone. Head with 3 pairs of ocellar setae, pair III almost as long as distance between hind ocelli, arising just anterior to these ocelli. Five pairs of almost equal postocular setae present (Fig. 2).

Pronotum with transverse lines of sculpture. Two pairs of long posteroangular setae present; outer pair a little longer than half as long as inner one; posterior margin with 4 pairs setae scarcely longer than discal setae (Fig. 2). Prosternal ferna almost connected at middle (Fig. 4). Mesonotum with median setae far from posterior margin; campaniform sensilla present. Metanotum with longitudinal striae and a pair of campaniform sensilla, median pair of setae at anterior margin (Fig. 3).

Fore wing first vein with 3–4 setae on distal half; second vein with complete row of setae (Fig. 8). Abdominal tergites III–VII with no sculpture medially; tergite VIII without posteromarginal comb (Fig. 5). Sternites without discal setae, abdominal sternum VII has the median pair of setae arising far ahead of posterior margin (Fig. 6).

Material examined: Fars province, Shiraz, 1♀, *Salsola baryosma*, 23.x.2019 (KM 1981).

Distribution in Iran: Fars province.

Distribution in the world: Iran, France, Spain and Morocco.

Remarks: Among the Iranian *Tenothrips*, *T. onondis* share with *T. discolor* in having campaniform sensilla on the metanotum. However, they are distinguished by the length of posteroangular setae on the pronotum (in *T. discolor*, these setae have almost the same length while the inner pair is considerably longer than the outer one in *T. onondis*).

Figs 1–8. *Tenothrips ononidis*, female; 1. Body; 2. Head and pronotum; 3. Meso and metanotum; 4. Prosternum; 5. Abdominal tergites VIII–X; 6. Abdominal sternites V–VII; 7. Antenna and 8. Fore wing.

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